

Electoral Technology and Democratic Consolidation in Nigeria, 1999-2024

*Jacho David Sunday Ph.D

Department of Political Science, Nasarawa State University, Keffi

**Corresponding author: Jacho David Sunday Ph.D*

Department of Political Science, Nasarawa State University, Keffi

Abstract

Since gaining traction as a tool for enhancing free, fair, credible elections and democratic consolidation, lots of financial and other resources have been committed to procure and deploy electoral or biometric technology (ET\BT). Reports on hand however present mixed pictures of its performances. While some scholars idolise or fetishise it as a sure and permanent cure for electoral challenges, others think otherwise. This paper therefore examines how far ET\BT has influenced Nigeria's electoral fortunes. Social construction theory of technology served as guide to the investigation. The theory argues that deployment of ET alone is not enough to bring about free, fair, acceptable and credible elections in society. Rather, it has to be combined with other forces. Data for the paper were generated from secondary sources like, books, journals, and position papers. Findings have it that undoubtedly, ET has been able to overcome some ills associated with manual electoral processes like voter impersonation, multiple registrations or voting as well as reduction of delay in voter registration and so on. The investigation equally found that ET is highly potentially open to manipulation by users since they are human beings who like other electoral stakeholders (such as contestants and political groups) may have their preferences in elections which may differ from those preferred by majority of electorates. Thus, it is recommended that a fine balance be struck between cautious deployment of ET in aspects that fall outside its purview and applications of manual processes where necessary. The need for regular and vibrant sensitisation of critical electoral stakeholders like officials handling elections be stepped up so as to minimize sentiments or biases influencing their official conducts.

Keywords: Technology, Democracy and Democratic consolidation.

Introduction

One of the greatest challenges that election stakeholders (like political parties, election management bodies, contestants, civil society organisations, electorates, election observers and indeed, officials of government among others) have contended with over the ages has been how to make election free, fair, credible and trustworthy. This is because, it is widely believed that once the exercise (election) attains above listed qualities, all key players (stakeholders) will accept the outcomes as choice of the majority and be willing to lend support to the leadership that emerges therefrom, thereby making elections credible; but, if otherwise, reverse will be the case. This is the consensus forged by Maendeleo Policy Forum, 2016; American Journal of Computer & Information Technology, 2018 & Jacho 2022. This view is consistent with earlier submission by Mozaffar (2002) cited in Jacho, Abdullahi & Wahal (2024) who persuasively sees electoral credibility as the Linchpin of democratic governance which underpins legitimacy of political systems and consolidation of democratic practices. Infact, the search for electoral credibility has been on in all liberal democracies across the world whether in Developed or Developing, Asian or African clime(s). The belief that flows therefrom is that once results of elections attain above standards, those entrusted with leadership will run affairs of wherever they belong accountably and transparently. It implies then that the leaders will regularly involve the electorates in conception, formulation and implementation of policies and or Programmes. Expectedly, the partnership between them (Leaders and electorates) will improve living conditions of the People. As a result of this partnership, individuals, groups and even institutions of

governance will equally like to democratize their activities. Ultimately, all individuals, groups and institutions (Governmental and Non-governmental) and so on of society will embrace democratic practices as the only way of conducting their activities. Democracy is then taken to new and noble heights or consolidated.

This most likely explains why Linz and Stephan (1996 cited in Wahab, unpublished, 2025) perceptively see democratic consolidation as the point when “democracy becomes the only game in town”. It (democratic consolidation) can then be said to be a state of being where all individuals, groups and institutions in society embrace accountability and transparency in all their conducts or activities regularly as opposed to authoritarianism. In view of the fact that democracy becomes a way of life, in fact a norm and tradition of Political actors (such as individuals, political parties governmental and non governmental organisations) in society, only persons popular among the people can be elected to represent them. The process(es) through which leaders are to be elected must therefore be free, fair and credible.

In efforts to evolve mechanisms through which credible and acceptable elections are held, governments across democracies in the world, Nigeria inclusive have emplaced measures such as electoral reform, increased voter education, improvement in funding of election as well as deployment of technology and so on. The focus of this paper is however the latter (deployment of electoral technology) so as to improve the quality of elections. The technologies/machines deployed for elections include: Electronic Voter Register (EVR), Automatic Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS), Optical Magnetic Recognition (OMR), Permanent Voters’ Card (PVC), Direct Data Capture Machines (DDCM) as well as INEC Voters Enrolment Device (IVED) Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) and INEC Results Viewing Centre (IREV) (Idowu, 2021). Otherwise referred to as Biometric Technology (BT), it became necessary to use so as to overcome the inadequacies of manual electoral activities such as destruction of ballot papers/boxes, multiple registration of voters, frequent voters’ impersonation, avoidable delays in registration of voters or even voting among others (Jacho, Abdullahi & Wahab, 2024; Idowu, 2021; Goar & Madigu, 2022).

Following deployment of ET/BT to promote free, fair, credible and acceptable elections, conversations have been raging among scholars concerning suitability or otherwise of the process (ET). However, given the endless arguments for or against it (ET), this paper suggests a fine balance between deployment of ET and modest application of manual processes in aspects where ET is unable to achieve intended goals. This paper is structured into six parts, beginning with this (1), Part two (2) captures conceptual clarification as the next part three highlights objectives of the paper, while the next (part four) reviews literature related thereto. Part Five (5) presents data generated in respect of the paper, while part six (6) summarizes and concludes same.

Objective

The broad objective of the paper is to examine the extent to which ET/BT has impacted on free and fair elections in Nigeria and by extension affected democracy in the country. However, the specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine how far ET has affected electoral violence and by extension democratic consolidation in Nigeria.
- ii. Discuss how far ET has impacted electoral litigations hence democratic consolidation
- iii. Discuss how extra- ET factors have affected elections, then democratic consolidation in Nigeria.

Methods

This paper employed explanatory research design in the investigation. It utilized secondary data from relevant textbooks, articles in journals and internet to content analyse information generated therefrom.

Conceptual clarification

Some key concepts used in the paper are operationalized with a view to establishing evolving their contextual meanings. These are:

Technology

A panoply of definitions is associated with the concept, a few of which are:

- i. The United Nations’ Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) refers to it as the technical know-how, tools and systems used by humans to manipulate their environment in order to meet their material needs and wants
- ii. Similarly, William (2008) sees it as the complex of knowledge tools and systems created by humans to manipulate their environment and improve human conditions.
- iii. Nye (2006) equally alludes to the fact that technology is an embodiment of ideas and skills which people craft into tools or machines to make their tasks simpler, faster and efficient, but, also a cultural activity that influences and is influenced by social, economic and political relationships which affect how power is distributed in society. Nye’s definition implies that though it (technology refers to skills, ideas including tools and machines made by man to solve his problems, it is usually fashioned to achieve those values and norms he cherishes. The problems could be social, economic, political or cultural. Examples that readily come to mind are Bimodal

Voters' Accreditation Systems (BVAC), Optical Magnetic Recognition (OMR), Automated Fingerprints Identification Systems (AFIS), Direct Data Capture Machine (DDCM).

Democracy

The concept is associated with several meanings, some of which are:

Lehtonen (2014) sees it as a system of government which emphasizes inclusion of electorates/people's opinions in decision making processes of society, while Lincoln (1809 cited in Jacho, Abdullahi & Wahab, 2024) said of it as "government of the people by the people for the people". For Dahl (2020), it (democracy) is a polyarchy whereby several groups in society access power and influence the decisions thereafter.

Above definitions imply that democracy means

- decision making about affairs of society taken by all and not a few
- in modern times, it is a system of government whereby a few people hold rein of affairs in trust (government) on behalf of the people (principals)
- such ones (government) are to regularly render account of their activities to the principals/people
- mechanism of periodic elections exists to subject government officials and activities to checks and balances.

The bottom line of democracy is to subject all major activities of government to control of the people which will improve their lots. Once this way of managing public affairs becomes accepted by most individuals, groups and indeed, institutions of society, democracy is taken to new heights or consolidated. This leads us to the concept of democratic consolidation.

Democratic Consolidation

Democracy is consolidated in society when most major activities of government are subjected to regular checks by the people transparently. It is a state or process whereby most political actors in society-individuals, groups, and institutions thereof subject important issues of government to public scrutiny and decisions so that government does only what people like and have suggested. As a matter of fact, it is at this stage as Schedler (2001) persuasively opines that democracy has become stable enough to prevent regression to authoritarianism or any other non-democratic form of governance. For Warren (2009), it is a crucial phase in the life of a democracy, where democratic norms, institutions and practices are deeply entrenched and widely accepted by all political actors, including the government, opposition and the citizenry. Linz and Stepan (1996) quite perceptively seize the point about democratic consolidation by saying of it as the point when it (democracy) becomes "the only game in town". To them (Linz and Stepan), democracy is consolidated when no significant political group seeks to overthrow the democratic regime or replace it with an authoritarian alternative. Example, when elections are held and some key players loose, they will not accept that the military is invited to take over the rein of affairs of the country. Rather, they will accept or prefer to serve as opposition and work hard towards recapturing power in subsequent elections.

Features of democratic consolidation

- i. democracy increasingly becomes a common currency or denominator for resolving many public issues in society
- ii. all critical public issues are subjected to public conversations before being conceived and implemented.
- iii. recourse to authoritarianism in all matters is abhorred and avoided by all key political actors in society.
- iv. Even when some key political actors loose elections, they don't incite violence and revolt.

Going by above features, democracy doesn't seem to be growing stronger or consolidating in Nigeria.

Literature review

Since gaining traction or favour as a very strong tool for enhancing free, fair, credible and acceptable elections, electoral, otherwise referred to as biometric technology has provoked endless conversations among Scholars and analysts. The discourses are conducted around two major strands of thought, viz: those who opine that deployment of technology in elections(s) will take the phenomenon to higher and desirable heights and on the other hand, opponents of the view that deployment of the technology can turn around the fortunes of elections positively.

Canvassing for increasing use of electoral or biometric technology to improve electoral outcomes in Africa, Maendeleo Policy Forum (2016) in its work titled "Deepening Democracy: Election Management and Stability in Africa's Divided Societies" commends technology for contributing tremendously to making elections more credible in African Countries where it has been deployed. Drawing data from Secondary Sources, the work admits some inadequacies associated with ET, but, submits that with improvements, it is capable of making elections more credible and acceptable in the continent. Equally persuaded by the potentials of ET in promoting free, fair and credible elections in Nigeria, Goar and Madugu (2023) in their article titled "Impact & Limit of Technology on Free, Fair & Credible Elections in Nigeria" opine that ET has made elections more credible in the country, although, bogged down by some challenges. Though, the paper draws

data from secondary sources, it is concluded with calls for improvements in areas of weaknesses to make elections in the country more credible. Going through the papers, one observes that they are not guided by any theory. Notwithstanding the positive contributions of ET/BT to electoral credibility and legitimacy, several scholars have criticized the so much confidence reposed in it (ET) for improving electoral credibility. Details as captured below: -

Mathe (2020) in his work titled “The Challenges and Opportunities of web 2.0 Elections: The Case of Zimbabwe” criticizes the tendency of over reliance on technology to resolve challenges associated with elections, because according to him, on its own technology cannot address ills associated with elections, as it is operated by humans who can manipulate same to produce results desired by the manipulators or managers of elections, not the actual will of electorates. According to him, there are issues in election which fall outside the competence of ET. It will appear or imply that issues like intimidation of voters, vote buying, lack of registration as a voter etc cannot be usefully handled by ET. As a matter of fact, Mathe argues that such issues are social in nature, not technological and so technology cannot be “always to the rescue”. This belief could have possibly made Castells (2004) to argue that “political Institutions and Democratic processes cannot experience the desired change via reliance on technology alone”. Joerges (1998) is even more forthright in saying that no matter the level of technology deployed for elections, human factors cannot be completely eradicated.

Similarly dissuaded by over reliance on technology for reliable and credible elections, Cheeseman, Lynch and Willis (2018) in an article captioned “Digital Dilemmas: The Unintended Consequences of Election Technology” observe that though deployment of electoral technologies is increasing across the world, it is a factor of “Fetishisation of technology” rather than the actual assurance of its ability to enhance credibility of elections. They further contend that while ET may improve electoral credibility, they tend to distract attention from ‘more traditional strategies’ of electoral frauds such as vote buying, gerrymandering, voters intimidation etc. which technologies are incapable of dealing with. The Study which generated data from both primary (vide interviews) and secondary sources concludes by cautioning users of ET to be more Careful before deploying same in elections.

Equally cautioning against wholesale confidence reposed in technology for enhancing credibility in elections, Russell and Zamfir (2018) in their work “ Digital Technology in Elections: Efficiency Versus Credibility” undertake examination of critical aspects of ET in which they suggest cautious management of it (ET) so as to set upto date voters’ register that will get rid of multiple voting in less developed countries where citizens lack reliable means of identification. They admit that electronic voting undoubtedly ensures fast counting of votes in addition to the potential that internet voting has increased turn out of voters at their convenience. Above benefits notwithstanding, the operators can use the machines to hack and intercept the operations thereby interfering with results of election. To them, this would explain why Estonia appears to be the only country that as deployed internet rooting presently. They therefore advise cautious deployment of the tool.

Another equally persuasive insight on the conversation concerning use of ET in election administration is the European Centre for Electoral Support (ECES, 2021) which conducted research on the “Challenges and opportunities of E-voting drawing lessons from Namibia, India, Brazil and Indonesia. The study adopted qualitative method in generating data involving indepth interviews, desk review and case studies. The aim was to highlight issues connected with implementation of E-voting. The study found out that while Brazil and India could produce the machines locally, Namibia lacks the capacity which raises questions over ownership. The investigation reveals that the countries studied ensured that a measure of control was inserted into the machines or software for monitoring its operations was installed therein. The paper further revealed that in Namibia and Brazil, the machines were always test-run during sub-national elections before application of same at the national level. Given both the opportunities and costs associated with deployment of ET, the paper recommends that countries deploy same with great care.

From the review undertaken above, the following lessons can be highlighted: -

- ET/BT has undoubtedly minimized or eliminated a lot of issues connected with multiple voting; registration as well as counting of votes and transmission of results to a central location/server electronically.
- It has also saved useful time used in voting/registration etc. manually.
- ET additionally encourages more voter turn out as delay in doing so is avoided/minimized.
- Ultimately, it enhances transparency in the electoral process thereby stepping up credibility of elections.

Resultantly, democracy is strengthened or consolidated. Above positives about ET notwithstanding, it is fraught with the following challenges:

- Technical glitches could affect some of the processes, a good example is the type that occurred during transmission of results of 2023 presidential election vide IREV to the server.
- Poor network
- Poor skills of some INEC officials to handle the ET
- Cost of Procuring ETs.

— Conflict between norms and traditions of the people with ETs

It is simply presumed that once modern ETs are procured for use of electoral staff (permanent and adhoc), without mobilizing and sensitizing them to understand and accept to use them (ETs), they will behave as expected. In other words, it is wrongly presumed that once the ETs are supplied for use by electoral officials without changing their attitude towards corruption, attachments to their tribes or religions, they will operate the machines as expected and give victory to candidates popularly elected by the electorates. Reality however doesn't reveal so in Nigeria. Electoral officials come from communities and some of the candidates contesting may hail from such places and given the level of attachment to primordial sentiments in the country, the officials saddled with electoral duties may prefer their people to win even if such ones are not popular.

What therefore appears more important is to mount vibrant and functional sensitization of people, especially those handling electoral duties to ensure that their allegiances go more to their duties (Nigeria) and not where they come from so that in discharging their duties, the staff will defend national cause rather than those of where they come from. It is upon this conviction that they will not accept to manipulate the ETs in favour of their ethnic or religious bed fellows when such candidates are not popular. To think that by merely imposing sophisticated ETs on officials of elections whose attitudes towards corruption and religious or ethnic sentiments have not been changed is simply a very tall day dream. This simply translates to what Cheeseman et al (2018) call fetishisation of technology or better still, technological determinism. As a matter of fact, such is bound to fail as has been the case in Nigeria. What appears more important is a fine relationship created between acquisition of technology and sufficient sensitization of election officials, as in the long run, successful deployment of ETs will depend on willingness and cooperation of the latter.

Having established the basis or foundation for successful deployment of ETs, it is appropriate at this point to examine theories that guide this paper. The paper finds rational choice and social construction of technology theories more appropriate.

Rational Choice theory

The theory was propounded in 1776 by renowned British Economist, Adam Smith. Rooted in economics, it believes that every consumer of goods or services and in this case INEC always makes critical decisions on which products or services to buy at which cost, when and how. Basic assumptions of the theory include:

- i. individuals are selfish and by implication make selfish decisions
- ii. consumers always make wise decisions to maximize their interests.
- iii. consumers' decisions are arrived at independently based on full information
- iv. all decisions take are always based on cost-benefit analysis as decisions are based on preferences, beliefs & constraints.
- v. decisions are made usually directed at achieving specific goals (Redfield, 2013).

Applying the theory to the issue on hand, it means that the decision to accept use of ET for elections or otherwise is taken by INEC and other critical electoral stakeholders, considering/putting into consideration the associated costs and benefits, noting that each option has implications. The theory argues essentially that INEC's decision to deploy ET was not senseless or random, but based on calculated benefits of enhancing credibility of elections and consolidating democracy in the country. Browning, Halcli & Webster (2000) argue that the theory, presupposes individuals or groups' regular involvement in cost-benefit analysis so as to ensure that groups or individuals arrive at the best decisions at least costs. Thus, all decision makers, INEC inclusive weighed the implication(s) of going for use of ETs in election for the purpose of enhancing electoral credibility and by extension consolidating Nigeria's democracy or refusing the deployment of ETs and risking the associated cost of lack of credibility in the electoral system. It can therefore be safely concluded that the decision to embrace deployment and use of ETs in Nigeria's electoral system was based on cost-benefit analysis.

Going by the arguments of the theory, it is very true that a lot of things were put into consideration before opting for deployment of ETs in the Country's electoral space, especially the enhancement of credibility of Nigeria's elections and the resultant improvement or growth in democracy therein. Above benefits notwithstanding, the theory suffers from:

- i. Inability to free Nigerian electorates, including INEC Officials from primordial sentiments of tribe, religion and or corruption. Thus, they do not act rationally during election.
- ii. Interplay of poverty and illiteracy combine to make Nigerians very vulnerable to manipulation during elections. So, electorates in Nigeria do not act rationally during elections.
- iii. Combined interplay of above listed factors with poor network and technical glitches reduced efficacy of rational choice theory, hence application of Social Construction Technology Theory as guide in the paper.

Social Construction of Technology Theory

It was propounded in 1987 by Pinch & Bijker. In their work titled "The Social Construction of Facts and Artefacts; or How the Sociology of Science and the Sociology of Technology might benefit each other", they submit that technology is

not a quick fix to attain electoral credibility, but rather is mediated by human action. This means that it is intended to serve man's purpose. Basic assumptions of the theory include: -

- it does not shape or determine human action, but is influenced by it.
- it (technology) is rather situated within and is influenced by a social context which means that human beings use or apply technology to solve their problems.

Mathe's criticism is appropriate here. According to him, it is wrong to over rely on technology to solve problems associated with elections as such require determination/political will to take place. As long as election stakeholders are not willing to deploy ET in transparent and accountable ways, elections can never be free, fair and credible. Rather, ET can be used negatively or manipulated to interfere with free, fair, credible and transparent elections. Dahl (1989) seizes the point quite persuasively here about ET that "the evolving technology is bound to be used somehow, for good or ill's".

As posited earlier, ET is only a tool invented to ease man's electoral efforts and therefore dependent on his skills preferences and will to succeed. And as Castells (2004) argues, "political institutions and democratic processes cannot experience the desired change via reliance on technology alone". This is because, it (ET) is a tool/device brought by man to achieve his goals which is to say that he can use such in pursuit of things he desires that could be for good or evil. Thus, ET should not be seen as always to the rescue of electoral credibility and democratic consolidation. What needs to be noted is that ET is an objective tool brought into being which depends on human ideas, skills and preferences of operators who can manipulate same to serve their ends. It must have been for this reason that Joerges (1999) observed that no matter the level of technology deployed for elections, human factors cannot be completely eradicated. Cheeseman, et al, 2018; Gelb and Diofasi, 2019; Idowu, 2021b; Idowu and Mimiko, 2020; Nwangwu et al, 2018) capture the point quite lucidly that technology is not able to resolve the challenges associated with poorly conducted elections.

Foregoing conversations concerning the place of ET in enhancing credibility of elections imply that though, ET can help overcome some challenges associated with manual elections, it (ET/BT) could be used negatively to undermine same due to technical glitches and man-made interventions. Therefore, as a tool brought in place by man to assist in elections, his level of skills values or preferences can go a long way in influencing whether he uses it well to enhance credibility of elections or otherwise. Thus, ET cannot be relied on singly to bring about credible elections. Rather, it has to be mediated by human supports. This explains why the theory of social construction of technology is more appropriate to guide this paper as a framework of analysis.

Weakness(es) of Social Construction theory of Technology

In spite of the strength of Social Construction Theory, it is faulted for being weak on account of the fact of its pessimism or disbelief in ability of ET to enhance credibility of elections. Reality however reveals that ET has actually assisted in enhancing credibility of elections, though fraught with some challenges.

Foregoing submissions imply that though ET has admittedly overcome many challenges associated with elections in many parts of the world and enhanced credibility including strengthening of democracy, it has some limitations which require delicate balances with human intervention to achieve desired results.

Relevance of Social Construction Theory to the Paper

The weakness of this theory notwithstanding, it is relevant to this paper, because of the fact that it stresses the need to strike a balance between manual electoral system and deployment of ET. This means that the two can be combined to make elections free, fair and credible thereby consolidating democracy in the country.

Analysis of results and discussion of findings

This paper set out to examine extent to which ET/BT has affected free, fair and credible elections and by extension, induced democratic consolidation, details as captured according to the objectives as:-

- i. Relationship between electoral violence, credible elections and democratic consolidation. One of the hallmarks of credible election is the latitude that it offers electorates to vote for candidates of choice without any fear (real or imaginary) of intimidation or attack before, during or after election. Once an electoral system is characterized by any form of violence, many electorates will be scared and therefore stay away from exercising their choice. During the period under review, there were several cases of thugs denying eligible electorates from voting or attacking and destroying election materials and people across various parts of Nigeria based on ethnic or religious identities. YIAGA Africa (2024:27) reports that across the width and breadth of Nigeria, there were several cases of electoral violence, as either electorates, election personnel, including materials were attacked during the Presidential, National Assembly as well as Governorship and House of Assembly elections. In one instance, YIAGA Africa (2024:28) reports the spate of 51 attacks and vandalisation of INEC materials and facilities in 15 states across Nigeria. Thus, the House of Representatives had to hold public hearing on such ugly developments. The reports further state that during the 2023 general elections in Nigeria, 65,699 uncollected Permanent Voters' Cards, 404 ballot boxes, 29 voting cubicles/polling booths, 30 megaphones as well as 57

election bags, 8 electric power generators were destroyed, including kidnap of election officials among others. As a matter of fact, this finding is consistent with reports of Kimpact Development Initiative (2022) which reveals clearly that the deployment of ET for elections in Nigeria shows increasing spate of violence in the country's electoral system since 2011. This is in line with the earlier findings of Uzodike & Onapajo (2019); Kassem & Osasona (2020); Oke & Atufu-Musa (2020); Ogbe & Ojie (2020) & Idowu (2021) cited in Wahab (2025) who all found out in their studies that ET has not been able to reduce violence in Nigeria's electoral space.

Above submissions imply that admittedly, ET has not been able to successfully reduce electoral fraud in certain aspects of the electoral system, but unable to completely eliminate such weaknesses as same (ET) has been manipulated by some political actors in Nigeria. To the extent that violence is still reasonably present in the country's electoral system, it means ET is unable to alone/singly bring down the problem of electoral crisis in Nigeria. It means ET must be combined with other tools to make elections free, fair, credible thereby consolidating the country's democracy.

- ii. How ET has impacted on electoral litigation and enhanced democracy or consolidated democracy. An election is said to be free, fair, credible and promotes democratic consolidation when all stakeholders, especially contestants and political parties accept results of elections without rancour and even congratulate winners after official announcement. Reality however shows in Nigeria that results of most elections at local, state and national levels are always contested in the tribunals (including the Supreme Court in cases of Gubernatorial and Presidential elections) across length and breadth of Nigeria. As a matter of fact, with exception of 2015 when President Goodluck Jonathan declined court action following announcement of General Muhammadu Buhari as the winner of the Presidential election, all other runners up since 1999 have always gone to tribunal and or court to contest results of Presidential elections. Admittedly, it should be noted that though seeking legal redress in respect of electoral contest is democratic and permitted by law, it is a clear sign of dissatisfaction with the electoral system. Even at the State and Local government Levels, litigations always flood election tribunals and or courts as the case may be. In advanced democracies like United States of America, United Kingdom and France among others, electoral litigations are usually much less, most times non existent after winners are announced.

It is expected that more than two decades of deployment of various technologies in conduct of elections in Nigeria should have strengthened or consolidated the country's democracy so that successive elections will witness lesser and lesser litigations. Unfortunately, this is not the case.

This finding is consistent with Kimpact Development Initiative (2023a) & Wahab (unpublished, 2025) that application of ET in Nigeria's election has not reduced electoral litigations. Therefore, it can be safely concluded that democracy cannot be said to have been deepened or consolidated.

- iii. Extra-ET/BT forces and Electoral Outcomes in Nigeria.
Some scholars (Nwogu, 2015; Kabiru et al, 2017; Nwagu et al, 2018; Omotayo & Adekunle, 2021 & Okwueze, 2022) expressed high level of optimism in ET/BT improving electoral outcomes very highly in Nigeria. But, after more than two decades of its application, it has become crystal clear that ET alone is incapable of doing so. Rather, it has to be combined with regular and functional dialogue with electoral stakeholders, including stiff penalties for electoral offenders as well as increased sensitization/enlightenment for election officials among others. This finding is consistent with the theory of Social Construction of Technology.

Forgoing conversations imply that though ET has reasonably reduced manipulations of results of elections, it is equally vulnerable to manipulation by officials of electoral bodies due to the fact that they are human beings and susceptible to a lot of social influences in society that could temper with results of elections as attested by the level of electoral violence and electoral related litigation. ET has therefore impacted on elections in the country only minimally. Thus, there is need to combine, improved versions of ET with other factors highlighted above for successful elections. So that democracy can be consolidated.

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